

Detection of Photovoltaic Panel Faults Using Convolutional Neural Networks

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Abstract

The shift to renewable energy is widely regarded as the only viable solution to reducing our dependence on fossil fuels. In this transition, Photovoltaic (PV) systems play a crucial role by offering a sustainable and efficient way to generate energy. However, to maximize the efficiency of PV modules and extend their lifespan, it's critical to detect defects early. Issues such as manufacturing flaws, cracks in the crystal structure of semiconductor materials, and wear from regular use can significantly reduce the performance of PV modules, causing operational problems. In this study, we used only polycrystalline images and analyzed Electroluminescence (EL) images to evaluate the performance of various deep learning models such as ResNet, DenseNet, and EfficientNet in classifying PV panel defects. To tackle the challenges of limited and imbalanced datasets, we applied transfer learning and data augmentation to enhance the models' accuracy. The experimental results showed that DenseNet121 outperformed the other models, achieving an accuracy of 90.60%, highlighting its potential for improving the maintenance and longevity of PV systems. These findings highlight the strong potential of CNN-based deep learning models to improve the monitoring and maintenance of PV systems, enabling early and precise defect detection.

Keywords: CNN, Solar Panel, PV, EfficientNet, ResNet, DenseNet

1. Introduction

Today, renewable energy sources provide the most significant contribution to reducing the demand for fossil fuel-based energy. The tremendous advancements in renewable energy production indicate that the dominance of fossil-based energy consumption in the sector will soon come to an end [1]. The largest share in renewable energy production undoubtedly belongs to solar energy-based facilities. According to reports by the International Energy Agency (IEA), fossil-based energy production is expected to lose its leading position in the sector by 2027 [2]. The increase in installed capacity of photovoltaic (PV) solar power plants plays a key role in this shift. The superior capacity growth in solar energy systems is attributed to advancements in high technology and efficiency in the production of polycrystalline and monocrystalline PV cells. Developed countries have doubled the capacities of their PV systems over the past few years. Location and climate conditions are among the most important factors affecting the efficiency and sustainability of PV systems. Another significant issue is the deterioration that can occur in PV cells during production or operation, which can impact system performance. Cracks, corrosion, and degradation caused by external factors in PV systems can sometimes lead to major problems that affect the entire system [3], [4].

Timely detection of faults in Photovoltaic (PV) power systems is crucial. Deep learning methods enable the detection of these defects in PV cells with very high accuracy. To detect faults in PV panels, various types of images, such as RGB, electroluminescence (EL), thermal, and infrared, are required [5]. Using these images, artificial intelligence models, trained with classification algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), can detect defects in the panels with high precision [6]. These deep learning models, based on image classification, typically require large amounts of labeled data and systems with high computational power [7]. In small datasets, techniques such as data augmentation and transfer learning are used to improve the overall performance of the models [8].

The most effective visualization technique for detecting production defects and failures caused by the degradation of the crystal structure in PV cells is electroluminescence (EL). Infrared imaging is also widely used since it visualizes defects in the cells differently [9], [10]. The success rate of AI models that use these images can vary

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depending on the quality of the images in the dataset [11], [12]. Since PV plants cover large areas, obtaining these images efficiently can be challenging and time-consuming. PV panel images can be captured using unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [13]. We observe an increase in studies in the literature focused on this topic. Additionally, validated datasets used by AI models for defect detection have become available [14], [15]. One of these is the ELPV dataset, a benchmark dataset containing EL images of monocrystalline and polycrystalline PV cells. The dataset includes 2,624 labeled EL images of PV cells with defect probabilities [16]. Akram and his team applied a specific data augmentation technique using the ELPV image dataset to detect defects in solar panels. Using a shallow artificial neural network model, they achieved an accuracy of 93.02% in classifying solar cells as functional or defective [17]. In 2020, Ahmad and his team proposed two different PV fault detection models based on CNN and SVM using offline data augmentation with the ELPV image dataset, demonstrating that the CNN classifier performed better with an accuracy of 91.58% [1].

In this study, various CNN models were used to detect defects on Electroluminescence (EL) images of PV cells. Specifically, the architectures of ResNet, DenseNet, and EfficientNet were focused on, and the performance of these models enhanced with transfer learning was evaluated. Data augmentation techniques were employed to improve the overall performance of the models on limited and imbalanced datasets.

2. Method

2.1 Deep Learning Algorithms

Deep learning has transformed the way we approach complex problems, allowing machines to learn from large amounts of data and recognize patterns that would be difficult for humans to detect. This is especially true in the field of image processing, where Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). CNNs mimic the way our own visual system works, analyzing images in layers and gradually focusing on the most important details. Their ability to automatically extract and understand features from images has made them invaluable, especially in industries like renewable energy, where precision and efficiency are crucial [18].

In this study, CNN models were used to detect defects in Electroluminescence (EL) images of photovoltaic (PV) cells, which are critical to solar energy production. These models, with different architectures and depths, were designed to recognize subtle flaws in PV cells that might otherwise go unnoticed. By using advanced techniques like transfer learning and data augmentation, the study aimed to boost the performance of these models, even when working with limited or imbalanced datasets [19].

2.2 CNN Models

ResNet (Residual Network): ResNet is a CNN architecture that tackles the challenges of training deeper networks by using residual connections. These connections help solve the issue of vanishing gradients, which often makes it hard to train very deep models. By doing so, ResNet makes it possible to create and train more complex networks. This approach is particularly effective for detecting defects in EL images of PV cells, as it allows the model to learn and interpret features at multiple levels, leading to more accurate results [20].

DenseNet (Densely Connected Convolutional Networks): DenseNet is a CNN architecture that stands out because each layer connects directly to all previous layers, creating a web of dense connections. This clever design boosts the reuse of features and improves the flow of gradients, which in turn enhances the model's ability to generalize and achieve higher accuracy. When it comes to detecting defects in PV cells, DenseNet excels thanks to its powerful capability to extract and classify detailed features, making it an effective tool for this task [21]. Figure 1 illustrates the DenseNet architecture.

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Figure 1 DenseNet Architecture

EfficientNet: EfficientNet is developed through a model scaling approach that optimizes the depth, width, and resolution of the network. This architecture aims to achieve high performance with lower computational resources. EfficientNet is known for its ability to deliver high accuracy even with small and imbalanced datasets, making it a suitable candidate for PV cell defect detection [22].

2.3 ELPV Data Set

The ELPV dataset is a key resource for studying PV cell defects, offering a collection of Electroluminescence (EL) images from both monocrystalline and polycrystalline PV cells. It features 2,624 images, each carefully labeled based on the likelihood of defects. These images are originally categorized into four groups: flawless, likely flawless, likely defective, and defective. For the purposes of this study, the dataset was simplified into two categories: "functional" and "defective." The dataset is divided into training and test subsets to help build and assess the performance of the models effectively.

Figure 2 Some sample poly images from ELPV dataset

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2.4 Transfer Learning

Transfer learning is a powerful technique that enhances the effectiveness of deep learning models, especially on small datasets, and has become widely used in recent years. The success of transfer learning is directly related to the similarity between the source and target datasets [23]. In particular, pre-trained deep neural networks on large-scale datasets have shown high performance when applied to smaller, specialized datasets, especially in computer vision tasks.

One of the main advantages of transfer learning is that it reduces the computational power required for training deep neural networks. Models pre-trained on datasets like ImageNet have demonstrated successful results even on tasks with few examples, and this method has been observed to shorten training times and improve overall model performance [24].

Transfer learning involves using the weights of a model pre-trained on large datasets for new and usually smaller datasets. In this study, CNN models (ResNet, DenseNet, and EfficientNet) pre-trained on extensive datasets like ImageNet were used. Transfer learning balanced the limited size of the dataset used for PV cell defect detection, accelerating the learning process and improving performance. The initial layers were frozen to ensure faster and more efficient training, while deeper layers were re-trained to learn features specific to PV cells.

2.5 Data Augmentation and Data Preprocessing

Data augmentation is a technique used to address the challenges posed by small and imbalanced datasets. By artificially increasing the variety of training data, it helps prevent models from underperforming. In this study, a range of augmentation methods was applied, from basic image manipulations like rotation, scaling, cropping, and flipping, to more sophisticated techniques such as color space adjustments and adding noise. These methods not only improved the model's ability to generalize but also helped mitigate the problem of overfitting.

The dataset was divided into three parts: training, validation, and testing. Specifically, 70% of the data was used for training, while the validation and test sets each took up 15%. This setup allows for a clear and reliable assessment of the CNN-based models' performance, as their ability to generalize is tested exclusively on the unseen test data. This approach helps ensure that the results are robust and trustworthy.

3. Results and Discussion

The experiments were carried out on a system powered by an Intel i9-14900K CPU and an Nvidia RTX 4090 GPU, using the PyTorch deep learning library. This setup offered the robust computing power needed to handle large, complex models, while also making the training process both fast and efficient. Over the course of training, the models were run for 300 epochs, with performance metrics carefully tracked at the end of each one. To speed up the process, we also applied optimization techniques and leveraged data parallelism.

The performance of the models was evaluated using four main metrics. Accuracy represents the proportion of correct predictions across all classes, providing an overall measure of the model's performance. Recall indicates the model's ability to correctly identify defective PV cells, emphasizing the reduction of missed detections. Precision focuses on the proportion of cells predicted as defective that are indeed defective, aiming to minimize false alarms. Finally, the F1 Score combines both recall and precision, offering a balanced measure that accounts for both the accuracy and precision of the model. The experimental results for the ELPV dataset are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Experimental results of CNN-based models on ELPV dataset

Model	Accuracy
ResNet34	0.8888
ResNet50	0.8672
DenseNet121	0.9060
DenseNet169	0.8888
EfficientNetv2-small	0.8854
EfficientNetv2-medium	0.8500

The experimental results, as detailed in Table 1, offer a clear picture of how various CNN-based models performed on the ELPV dataset for detecting defects in photovoltaic panels. DenseNet121 emerged as the top performer, achieving an impressive accuracy of 90.60%. Its ability to capture intricate and subtle details in Electroluminescence (EL) images sets it apart. Both ResNet34 and DenseNet169 closely followed with accuracies of 88.88%, demonstrating their strong potential for defect detection in this context. EfficientNetv2-small also performed well, reaching an accuracy of 88.54%, though it fell short of surpassing DenseNet121. On the lower end, ResNet50 and EfficientNetv2-medium scored 86.72% and 85.00%, respectively.

These findings underscore DenseNet121's suitability for detecting defects in PV cells, thanks to its densely connected layers that enhance feature reuse and learning. While EfficientNet is typically designed for computational efficiency, its performance may have been limited by the smaller, imbalanced dataset used in this study, which hindered its ability to fully leverage its model scaling capabilities. In conclusion, DenseNet121 stands out as the most reliable and effective model for improving the detection and maintenance of defects in photovoltaic systems.

3.4 Discussion

The experimental results highlight how crucial model architecture is in detecting defects in PV panels. DenseNet121's impressive performance is largely due to its densely connected layers, which allow for more efficient reuse of features and smoother gradient flow during training. This structure enables the model to generalize more effectively, particularly when identifying small and intricate defects.

Although EfficientNet is known for optimizing depth, width, and resolution, it did not surpass DenseNet or ResNet in accuracy in this study. This suggests that the dataset's size and imbalance may have affected EfficientNet's performance, as it typically excels with larger datasets. Despite the use of transfer learning and data augmentation to address these challenges, DenseNet121 remained the top-performing model.

These findings indicate that DenseNet121 is highly reliable for defect detection in PV panels, offering both accuracy and consistency. Future research could benefit from using larger, more balanced datasets to potentially enhance the performance of architectures like EfficientNet. Moreover, investigating how these models perform in real-time industrial settings would provide valuable insights into their scalability and practical application for maintaining the efficiency of PV systems.

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4. Conclusion

In this study, we assessed the performance of various CNN-based deep learning models, including ResNet, DenseNet, and EfficientNet, for detecting defects in PV panels using Electroluminescence (EL) images. The results indicated that DenseNet121 achieved the highest classification accuracy at 90.60%, outperforming the other models. While EfficientNet is typically recognized for its computational efficiency, it did not surpass DenseNet in this context. These findings suggest that DenseNet121 is a robust architecture for identifying defects in PV cells, offering significant potential to enhance the monitoring and maintenance of PV systems, thereby ensuring their long-term efficiency and reliability. Future research could focus on integrating additional advanced CNN architectures and utilizing larger, more balanced datasets to further improve defect detection in PV panels. Moreover, investigating the real-time deployment of these models in industrial settings could provide important insights into their scalability and practical application.

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